

FORMATION OF AN INNOVATIVE ECONOMY IN THE REPUBLIC

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Annotation: It is characterized by a further strengthening of efforts to modernize the economy being implemented in Uzbekistan, the role of innovation in the market economy, ensuring continuity and increasing the scope of innovative processes in the field of production and service. In the context of the globalization of the world economy, Uzbekistan's innovative activity is considered to be due to macroeconomic and active investment policies, developed foreign experience and mechanisms to increase the attractiveness of the investment climate, which are being implemented efficiently and consistently by the state. Our President Sh.M.Mirziyoyev said that " creating an atmosphere of innovation in the worldview of our people is our most important task. As long as there is no innovation, there will be no competition, no development in any area. They said that if we do not widely promote changes in this field to our people, and do not develop skills in people, we cannot step even with the intensity of today's era and the unprecedented achievements of Science and technology.

Keywords: innovation in the economy, effective competition, privatization, innovation advanced technology, innovation, innovative technology, human capital.

To know the place of innovation in the economy, first of all, it is necessary to create an effective competitive environment. In Uzbekistan, the main place in the policy of the state aimed at forming a competitive environment is occupied by privatization, the emergence of other forms of ownership at the expense of state property. As a result of privatization, firstly, property is transferred into the hands of its owners, and secondly, it creates an atmosphere of a multi-billion dollar economy and competition. No matter what model of economic development the countries of the world choose, the position of the national economy in the world economy is determined by the degree of its competitiveness.

In the following years, along with scientific and practical literature in the field of Economics and the words “innovation” and “Advanced technology” in many scientific works, the terms “innovation” and “innovative technology” are also used on a large scale. The term “Innovation”, used in so many pulleys, conventions and scientific councils, means in Latin innovus (in – novus – depending on innovation), and it can be used as synonyms with the terms “innovation” and “advanced technology”.

The activity of enterprises within the framework of innovative activities is determined by how well their connection with the above-mentioned innovative organizations is established. In the process of creating innovations, innovative firms should provide information in the fields of Science, Technology, Technology and economics, and achieve financial, legal and political support. That is why, in a knowledge-based economy, the infrastructure of innovation or creativity will be of great importance. Therefore, also, we are not mistaken if we say that increasing the demand and sensitivity of the economy to innovation is one of the main goals of modern countries, including Uzbekistan. At the end of the 20th century and the beginning of the 21st century, efforts began to achieve innovative changes in all aspects of the life of society.

One of the most fundamental factors in the development of an innovative economy in Uzbekistan is undoubtedly human capital and its development in accordance with the requirements of the time. This human capital should be highly sensitive and aspiring to innovation, able to deeply understand new technologies, master the basics of science related to this, and be able to apply their knowledge to production. The goal of innovation should have a clear shape and be able to be measured. Behind the emergence of innovations lies the extremely hard work that has been carried out for many years. But often, than creating innovation, it becomes an extremely difficult issue to absorb.

- The final result of the creation of a post-industrial economy is the organization of a full-fledged innovative economy and should be the main strategic development direction of the economy of the same country. The formation of new types of scientific and practical knowledge and the effective use of innovative technologies created on their basis in the direction of socio-economic development of the state are the basis of the country's role in the world community and national disenchantment. 80-95% of the growth of gross domestic product (YIM) in developed Daves corresponds to the knowledge reflected in technology and technology. That is why we can say that the main signs of the modern innovative economy are:

- * Availability of modern information technologies and computerized systems in all sectors of the economy;
- * The presence of a developed modern infrastructure that will ensure the creation of a developed national information Reserve;
- * Rapid computerization and automation of production and management processes in all spheres of public life;
- * Creation of an extremely flexible system of training and retraining of qualified scientific and technical personnel in accordance with modern innovative requirements on a global scale.

Our esteemed First President I.A. As Karimov noted, "the implementation of deep structural transformations is one of the most important conditions for achieving macroeconomic stability, ensuring sustainable economic growth and well-being of the population of Uzbekistan in the future, integration into the world economic system." Stopping the rollback of production until the necessary structural changes take place in the economy remains the most important goal. In order to prevent the loss of our priceless wealth, we must abandon the technological lag and inefficient production process. After all, until the capital is renewed, there will be no technological development. But since the capital is new, and the technology of its work is old, its effect is also not felt, i.e. we can find that the role of innovation is invaluable both in the economies of developing and developed countries.

Modern approaches to economic development are important. The action strategy for the five priority areas of Uzbekistan's development for 2017-2021 also provides for the continuation of institutional and structural reforms to strengthen macroeconomic stability and maintain high economic growth rates, increase the competitiveness of the national economy, modernize and accelerate the development of agriculture, reduce state participation in the economy, aimed at further development and liberalization of the economy., It provides for the active attraction of foreign investment in economic sectors and regions of the country by protecting the rights of private property and further strengthening its priority position, stimulating the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, integrated and balanced socio-economic development of regions, districts and cities, improving the investment climate.

In this direction, the following priorities are set:

increasing the openness and competitiveness of the economy;

- development of economic independence;
- strengthening macroeconomic stability;

- modernization and diversification of leading manufacturing industries;
- reforming the financial and banking sector;
- further expansion of foreign economic relations;
- active attraction of foreign investments.

Based on the above considerations, I will briefly highlight a number of main works and measures that need to be taken from my point of view on the formation and development of an innovative economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan:

Creation of an interdepartmental commission to accelerate the formation of an innovative economy in the republic and the introduction of a special type of innovation tax (for example, in the amount of 1% of the income of each enterprise) to conduct its financial activities and endow it with the main powers when performing most of the following works to accelerate innovation in the republic;

- Studying, collecting, bringing to the attention of the broad masses of the population all the technological innovations that are important to us in developed countries and their rapid implementation in the sectors of the economy of the republic;
- Copy innovative innovations introduced in the republic's economic sectors to all other industries as quickly as possible, that is, to carry out internal technology transfer;
- Providing the best working conditions, material and financial resources to organizations or firms engaged in the creation of renewable, cheap and environmentally friendly energy sources and equipment;
- Constant communication to the general public of news and benefits of the innovative economy based on knowledge in the media, as well as all new information about modern innovative equipment;
- Creation of an effective national innovation system that provides economic, legal and organizational conditions for the speedy transition of Uzbekistan to the innovative path of activity.

List of used literature:

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